

Supplementary Materials: A Systematic Review of MLOps Tools: Tool Adoption, Lifecycle Coverage, and Critical Insights

ZAKKARIJA MICALLEF, KEERTHIGA RAJENTHIRAM, and ILIAS GEROSTATHOPOULOS, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, The Netherlands

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1 Data Availability

To support transparency and replicability, all data artefacts from this systematic literature review are provided alongside this supplementary document. The accompanying data is available in two formats: a spreadsheet file (`Literature_Sources.xlsx`) and a web archive (`Literature_Sources.html`). Both contain identical content, though the web format preserves readability better when viewing lengthy cell contents. The files contain the following sheets:

- **Papers Selection:** The initial pool of 96 papers screened from the first ten pages of Google Scholar results, including inclusion/exclusion decisions and reasons for exclusion.
- **Selected Papers:** The final corpus of 41 primary studies after applying selection criteria and snowballing, with publication metadata.
- **Extraction:** Raw data extraction for each tool mentioned in the primary studies, including reported uses, pipeline phases covered, benefits, limitations, and dependencies.
- **Synthesis:** Aggregated tool data showing mention counts, component mappings, and categorisation decisions.
- **MLOps Tools:** Final list of MLOps tools with their categories and descriptions.

2 Study Selection Process

Figure 1 illustrates the systematic literature review process following the PRISMA guidelines [1].

3 MLOps Lifecycle Categories

Table 1 summarises the MLOps lifecycle categories that emerged from the primary studies discussed in this section. Figure 2 shows the distribution of tools across these categories.

4 MLOps Tool Descriptions

This section provides detailed descriptions of all MLOps tools identified in the systematic review, organised by their primary category.

4.1 Infrastructure and Supporting Services

Apache Airflow is an open-source platform for orchestrating production workflows and data pipelines [2].

Argo Workflow is a container-native workflow engine for orchestrating parallel jobs on Kubernetes [3]. By combining Argo Events for webhook-triggered workflows and Argo Workflow for execution, developers can automate the full ML lifecycle in a reproducible, scalable, and hands-off manner. This includes training, evaluation, and deployment. While production environments can benefit from such pipelines for mature, production-ready teams, it is not recommended to incorporate such an environment in the early stages of ML services or businesses [3].

Kubeflow Pipelines handles managing and orchestrating containerised workloads [4] while taking care of model training, deployment, and coordination [5]. Since it runs on top of Kubernetes, it lets users codify preprocessing, training, and deployment steps in a single UI and execute many pipelines in parallel. Because every component ships as a Kubernetes resource, the same pipeline runs on-prem or in any managed Kubernetes service. It also has auto-scaling pods, notebook sessions provided by Jupyter, experiment tracking, hyperparameter tuning, and pluggable serving (Kubeflow’s own KServe or other solutions such as Seldon Core), which all sit behind the central dashboard.

Fig. 1. PRISMA flow diagram showing the study selection process. Starting from 9,100 Google Scholar results, 96 records were identified after initial filtering. Following screening and filtering, 27 articles were included, with 69 excluded. Forward snowballing added 12 articles and backward snowballing added 2, resulting in a final corpus of 41 articles.

Prefect Core is a pipeline orchestrator with a modern Python API that keeps code readable and flexible when workflows are highly dynamic [6].

ZenML links the orchestration layer with an artefact store so that a stack can swap orchestration, or any other component, without rewriting user code [7].

CML enables CI/CD for ML projects. It wires continuous integration to ML experiments, tracking changes and auto-generating metric reports [8].

TensorBoard is TensorFlow's official visualisation toolkit, offering interactive exploration of computation graphs, layer structures, and distributions of weights and biases through histograms. TensorBoard also provides real-time plotting of training metrics such as loss and accuracy over time [9].

Table 1. MLOps lifecycle categories observed in the primary studies

Component	Responsibility
Orchestrator	Provides system-wide orchestration and schedules multiple models while balancing throughput and latency.
Raw Data Store	Holds raw source data; needs specialised versioning tools because datasets exceed typical Git size limits.
Data Preprocessor	Transforms, cleans, and validates data before it becomes training input.
Dataset Repository	Stores and versions datasets; relies on large-file platforms.
Feature Store	Computes, stores, and serves reusable features with low latency.
Artefact Repository	Keeps packaged or containerised ML components that include a model.
ML Metadata Repository	Tracks training metadata for experiment tracking and model performance.
Code Repository	Versions source code, configuration files, and related artefacts.
Model Repository	Versions trained models together with basic metadata such as version numbers.
ML Training Pipeline (Online)	Automates continuous model training at runtime in production.
ML Experiment Pipeline (Offline)	Supports manual experimentation and training during design time.
MLOps User Interaction Manager	Enables interaction between the MLOps team and the platform.
ML Pipeline Editor	Builds, tests, and packages pipeline code into containers or similar environments.
Model Deployer	Deploys a trained model and its dependencies to production.
Model Evaluator	Measures and assesses model performance.
Runtime Model Monitor	Continuously watches serving performance and infrastructure metrics.
Visualisation	Presents dashboards and graphs for experiments, metrics, and system status.
End-to-End	Tools designed to address multiple lifecycle stages rather than a single component; in practice, none achieves complete coverage.
Managed End-to-End	Cloud-managed platforms that aspire to span the full workflow with integrated infrastructure and monitoring; despite their broad scope, auxiliary services are still needed for complete lifecycle coverage.

4.2 Managed End-to-End Platforms

AzureML is a managed end-to-end service; users still provision the workspace, storage, networking, and container registry either interactively or through infrastructure-as-code [10].

AWS SageMaker is Amazon’s cloud platform for building, training, tuning, and deploying models in a hosted production environment [11].

ClearML provides semi-automated experimental run tracking and auditing, capturing comprehensive metadata, parameters, and metrics across popular Data Science tools. It relies on a dedicated central web server underpinned by a MongoDB database, an Elasticsearch deployment, and cloud object storage for artefact archiving, enabling end-to-end traceability and auditability of experiments [12].

4.3 End-to-End Platforms

MLflow is an end-to-end tool made of multiple modules [13] which was initially started as an open-source platform to provide comprehensive experiment tracking capabilities [14][15][7][16]. It has grown to cover most of the MLOps pipeline through the inclusion of the following components. The *MLflow Tracking* component records parameters, metrics, and artefacts for every run [12], ensuring a complete workflow history. *MLflow Projects* encapsulate data science code and dependencies, enabling reproducible execution across diverse environments. *MLflow pipeline* involves processing, cleaning, transforming, training models, and evaluating them, ensuring large-scale ML model deployment. *MLflow Models* then offers a standardised structure for packaging machine learning models and facilitates seamless deployment in various serving infrastructures [13]. Finally, *MLflow Registry* serves as a unified model store, providing

Fig. 2. MLOps tool count grouped by category

versioning, annotation, stage transitions, and the promotion of specific model versions to “Production” for batch or real-time inference [15][17]. Autologging further streamlines experiments by automatically capturing parameters and metrics from supported ML libraries [7].

Neptune.ai positions itself as a complete platform that spans data versioning, testing, deployment, and monitoring [18].

Pachyderm offers GUI-based notebook services, experiment tracking, and hyperparameter tuning [19].

Polyaxon is an open-source, Kubernetes-native end-to-end MLOps platform focused on experiment tracking, visualisation, parallel executions and hyperparameter optimisation. Its main focus is parallelisable experiment tracking, where it attempts to provide computationally efficient mechanisms for running and interpreting parallel ML experiments at scale. While Polyaxon’s core and experimentation tools are open source, its automation and management features are not [19].

TensorFlow Extended (TFX) offers a production-grade pipeline implementation for TensorFlow models [20].

Google Vertex AI is part of GCP, merging AutoML and AI Platform behind one API, client library, and UI [21][10]. The Workbench offers Jupyter notebooks [22] and AutoML streamlines training, experiment tracking, and metadata management. A Model Registry manages versions for online or batch prediction, while the Pipeline view visualises step dependencies, integrated logging, and monitoring track performance over time.

4.4 ML Training

Katib is part of Kubeflow. It automates hyperparameter tuning across frameworks including TensorFlow, MXNet, PyTorch, and XGBoost [23].

4.5 Storage and Versioning

Weights & Biases is cited as an ML metadata repository, yet the sources offer no elaboration [7].

Dagshub hosts data repositories and models for collaborative versioning. Some authors store all pipeline outputs remotely in it [15][24].

DVC extends Git to manage large datasets and model files, enabling version control of large data alongside code [15] [25] [14] [13] [26] [27][20][4]. Consequently, its Git-like workflow simplifies adoption for users familiar with Git [25]. DVC's pipeline feature modularizes data processing into stages with explicit input-output dependencies and parameterisation, ensuring reproducibility, automation, and reusability across projects [25]. It also supports experiment tracking and storing metadata within Git, while actual data resides in DVC storage, with metadata files orchestrating data retrieval [8].

Feast provides both offline and online feature storage, keeping historical as well as live data in sync [16]. One paper mislabels it as a performance monitoring tool [9].

GTO is Iterative's GitOps-based model registry. It eliminates the need for separate servers or databases by leveraging Git and DVC repositories and provides streamlined support for promoting models through designated repository branches and stages [8].

4.6 Inference

Metaflow is a framework for creating and executing data science workflows in local environments and scaling them to the cloud with ease [12].

KServe originates from the Kubeflow ecosystem and wraps models as web services on Knative/Istio. This results in autoscaling, isolation, and an event-driven path to downstream monitoring [5][20][23].

BentoML is a model serving tool that bundles a trained model and its dependencies into a production-ready service [12][17].

Seldon Core is a model deployment tool that exposes models as web services [6] with robust support for Kubernetes [5].

Evidently is an open-source model monitoring library that generates predefined monitoring reports with a few lines of code. It can automatically detect drift in input data, target values, and predictions, and supports multi-model dashboards by calculating metrics across multiple models with a single monitor [24][16][5].

5 Tool Benefits and Limitations

This section presents detailed benefits and limitations for each MLOps tool category, extracted and synthesised from the primary studies.

Table 2. Summary of MLOps Tools: Infrastructure and Supporting Service (Orchestrators)

Tool	Benefits	Limitations
Apache Airflow	B1 Open source (Apache 2.0) [2]. B2 Intuitive web interface for visualising/monitoring workflows [2].	L1 Complex installation/configuration in production [2]. L2 Recommended installation method is complicated [2].
Kubeflow Pipelines	B3 Cloud-agnostic; runs on any Kubernetes provider [5, 19, 20, 23]. B4 More mature and ML-specialised than Flyte, Airflow [20]. B5 Abstracts dynamic workload scaling via Kubernetes [28]. B6 Full end-to-end solution with Notebooks, Pipelines, Katib [19, 29]. B7 Accessible, configurable UI dashboard [19, 30]. B8 Strong multi-user isolation security [19].	L3 Difficult setup; non-trivial learning curve [19, 31]. L4 Can feel bloated vs. focused solutions [31]. L5 Out-of-date documentation [19].
ZenML	B9 Simple local setup (three commands) [7]. B10 Auto-deploys local MLflow server [7]. B11 Easily expandable orchestration [7].	L6 Incomplete user management [7].
Argo Workflow	B12 Straightforward artefact storage/transfer between tasks. B13 Fully automated, reproducible, scalable E2E pipelines.	L7 Developers must manage containerisation complexity. L8 Requires deep Kubernetes knowledge.

Table 3. Summary of MLOps Tools: Managed End-to-End Platforms

Tool	Benefits	Limitations
AzureML	B14 Code-free drag-and-drop data cleaning [10]. B15 Quick setup; robust security (network protection, RBAC) [10]. B16 Most complete security features among cloud platforms [10].	L9 Commercial; requires Azure subscription [10].
SageMaker	B17 Robust/intuitive; feature parity with Azure ML; model registry, feature store, lineage tracking, CI/CD deployment [10, 11]. B18 Easy scalable training; reduced ops overhead [32]. B19 Seamless AWS integration including SSO [10, 11]. B20 Abstracted model tuning tools [11].	L10 Commercial licence required [9]. L11 Requires programming skills; less comprehensive docs [9]. L12 Additional work if not using AWS IAM/SSO [10].
Google Vertex AI	B21 AutoML, Jupyter in Workbench, model registry, pipelines, monitoring/logging [21]. B22 Central UI with visualised workflow dependencies [22]. B23 Flexible scalability; easy Kubernetes cluster setup [22].	L13 Dataset prep is “painful”; no drag-and-drop vs. Azure/AWS [10]. L14 Lacks robust IAM/workspace separation [10]. L15 Commercial pay-as-you-go model.

Table 4. Summary of MLOps Tools: End-to-End Platforms

Tool	Benefits	Limitations
MLflow	B24 User-friendly UI with visualisation and intuitive dashboard [14, 15, 26]. B25 Fully open-source; self-hostable; native container support [7, 12]. B26 Strong community; used by major companies [6, 7]. B27 Comprehensive documentation [6]. B28 Robust experiment tracking: metrics, artefacts, hyperparameters, dataset versions [15, 25, 29]. B29 Autologging; integrates with monitoring tools [4, 7, 13, 15]. B30 Flexible storage: S3, Azure Blob, GCS, SFTP, NFS, SQL [26].	L16 Requires dedicated server for collaboration [12, 25]. L17 No automatic data versioning [25, 26]. L18 No built-in resource alerting [12]. L19 No RBAC or user isolation [7, 26]. L20 Lacks native collaboration/auto-deployment [26]. L21 Some enterprise features require licence [9].
Neptune	B31 Easy setup; integrates with Colab, Git, Docker [9, 18]. B32 Complete platform: monitoring, versioning, testing [18]. B33 Open-source [9]. B34 Monitoring capabilities [18].	L22 Requires basic programming skills [18].
Pachyderm	B35 GUI notebooks, experiment tracking, HPO [19]. B36 Simple experiment parallelisation [19].	L23 Requires cloud storage/Helm knowledge [19]. L24 Heavy filesystem overhead [19]. L25 Lacks out-of-the-box solutions.
Polyaxon	B37 Basic Helm/K8s operator knowledge sufficient [19]. B38 Meticulous audit trail for reproducibility [19].	L26 No out-of-the-box scaling [5]. L27 Weaker community than Pachyderm/Kubeflow [19].
TFX	B39 Automates retraining, evaluation, deployment [22]. B40 Distributed computing support [22]. B41 Portable; runs on Airflow etc. [22].	L28 Requires TensorFlow [20].

Table 5. Summary of MLOps Tools: Storage & Versioning

Tool	Benefits	Limitations
Dagshub	B42 Facilitates collaboration/versioning [15]. B43 Bypasses GitHub size limits; integrates with DVC/MLflow [4, 15]. B44 Free integrated MLflow server; unified storage [4, 24].	No limitations reported.
DVC	B45 Git-like workflow eases adoption [25]. B46 Modular stages ensure reproducibility [25]. B47 Single-command pipeline execution via DagsHub [33]. B48 Caching for unchanged stages [8]. B49 Flexible storage (GDrive, S3, HTTP) without dedicated server [25].	L29 Manual updates for external data [25]. L30 File-level versioning costly for frequent changes; unsuited for SQL [25].
GTO	B50 GitOps-based registry; no separate DB needed [8]. B51 Model promotion to specific stages [8]. B52 Integrates with DVC/CML [8].	No limitations reported.
MinIO	B53 S3-compatible; optimised for AI [7]. B54 Stores ZenML/MLflow artefacts [18, 25].	No limitations reported.
Weights & Biases	B55 Real-time tracking with hardware monitoring [7]. B56 Free tier: unlimited runs, 100GB storage, HPO, model registry [7].	L31 Requires registration/licence; free plan for personal only [7]. L32 Server-side proprietary; limited self-hosting [7]. L33 Advanced programming knowledge needed [7, 18].
Feast	B57 Offline/online feature storage for historical and live data [16]. B58 Feature reuse across projects [9]. B59 MLflow integration [16]. B60 Open-source [9].	L34 Requires advanced programming [9]. L35 Complicated integration [9].

Table 6. Summary of MLOps Tools: Inference (Model Serving)

Tool	Benefits	Limitations
BentoML	B61 Open-source; supports TF, PyTorch, Keras, XGBoost [12, 17]. B62 Auto micro-batching; cloud-native deployment [12].	L36 Inference-only; no auto-deployment like KServe/Seldon [5, 12, 20].
KServe	B63 Auto-wraps models as web services; Kubeflow integration [5]. B64 Scalable, isolated deployments; HTTP/gRPC support [5, 23].	No limitations reported.
Seldon Core	B65 Pre-packaged inference servers; robust K8s support [6]. B66 Advanced Prometheus metrics [6].	No limitations reported.
Evidently	B67 Monitors data, target, prediction drift [16, 24]. B68 Few-line predefined reports [24]. B69 Multi-model metrics in single monitor [5]. B70 Prometheus/Grafana integration [16]. B71 Auto-logs to MLflow [16].	L37 Tabular data only; use Alibi Detect for images/text [5].

Table 7. Summary of MLOps Tools: Inference (Model Deployment)

Tool	Benefits	Limitations
Metaflow	B72 Local workflows scale easily to cloud [12]. B73 Rigorous checkpointing for tracking/logging [12]. B74 AWS integration; native parallelisation via Batch [12].	No limitations reported.
Streamlit	B75 Simple cloud deployment interface [24]. B76 Convenient GitHub integration [24].	L38 1GB limit for public apps [24].
CML	B77 Auto-tracks ML experiments/modifications [8]. B78 Generates comprehensive metric reports [8]. B79 Reports displayed in PR comments [8].	No limitations reported.

Table 8. Summary of MLOps Tools: Infrastructure and Supporting Services

Tool	Benefits	Limitations
Gradio	B80 Interactive web interfaces without HTML/CSS/JS [4].	No limitations reported.
TensorBoard	B81 Visualisation for graphs, histograms, metrics [9]. B82 Full exploration/visualisation functionality [9]. B83 Open-source; multi-tool integration [9].	L39 Requires TensorBoard familiarity [9].

Table 9. Summary of MLOps Tools: ML Training

Tool	Benefits	Limitations
Katib	B84 HPO for TensorFlow, MXNet, PyTorch, XGBoost [23]. B85 Seamless Kubeflow integration [23].	No limitations reported.

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